

Fieldnotes: Short Articles and Field Reports

Site near Hillfort of Souls

August 30, 2011 | by Alfredo Pirondini

The Author describes the Archaeological site near Hillfort of Souls (in Ligurian Language: Castelliere delle Anime), Rocca di Perti, Finale Ligure (Western Liguria, Italy), its orientation, petroglyphs, ponds for water harvesting and neighboring geological formations for any links with the site. A brief analysis on the possible use and dating of the finds on site completes the work.

[site_near_finale_ligure_aia.pdf](#)

Website:

<http://ilfinalese.blogspot.com/>

Site near Hillfort of Souls

Author: Alfredo Pirondini

Summary

The Author describes the site near Finale Ligure (Western Liguria, Italy), its orientation, petroglyphs, ponds for water harvesting and neighboring geological formations of interest for any links with the site. A brief analysis on the possible use and dating of the finds on site completes the work.

Description

This is a particular bioclastic limestone rock formation dating from the Miocene period (Stone Final), located near the Castelli delle Anime (i.e. Hillfort of Souls) of Perti (Finale Ligure - Italy).

The complex has a characteristically "U" shaped structure, with opening facing at east and is located 342 m above sea level, coordinates: 44°11'36.420"N; 8°18'44.100"E.

Currently (the last survey the author goes back to March 2011) the area is overrun with vegetation, which often hides and / or hinders the exploration of the site.

The formation resembles a Greek theater so arranged: a rock to the west about 180 cm high, with flat surface (about 4 square meters, presenting grooves and cups; the south wall is separated from the preceding by a "corridor" about 2 m wide, leading into a wooded area.

On this wall are carved small steps that invite the visitor to climb.

Once on top of this wall, follow it east about 4 meters, you reach a rocky crevice elliptical, with a larger diameter positioned along the east-west axis, containing water, named Pozza d'Acqua Perenne (i.e. Perennial Water Well).

This name finds its justification in the fact that, within the well, water is always present, even during a dry year. Continuing the climb, you reach the top of a cliff, where you can see the presence of a large pool, bottom and sanded smooth, able to collect rainwater leaking from a channel "to lose" when it reaches that level.

From this rocky cliff you can admire the beautiful landscape and the so-called "Formaggette" (i.e. The Cheeses), a geological formation (like large loaves of cheese stacked) south of our vantage point.

The east wall is difficult to explore, but it might conceal, underneath the thick vegetation, finds interesting as a careful observation.

At this point, we pose some problems: not least the significance and dating of the finds on site and their possible relationship with the inhabitants of the Rock of Perti.

Indeed, we know that the Hillfort, better known as Village of Souls, the core of Iron Age hill (around the tenth century BC), has more ancient origins: it can be found in the caves surrounding tracks dating back some 8000 years ago, belonging probably to the Neolithic.

The channels and the plates placed on Ciappo Western Wall, as well as the large pool (with gutter attached) to the south are, presumably of anthropogenic origin. Not so you can tell the water well sustainability and cheeses that are geological formations due, presumably, the erosive action of meteoric phenomena.

These formations could attract the attention of the prehistoric frequenters of the area.

On the one hand, Cheeses, located at sunrise, the observer, could serve as a natural standing stones (such as the Idol of Penn of Ponci Valley). Across the Perennial Water Well and large pool would provide a water reserve, very valuable in a place like this.

As regards, however, the petroglyphs of eastern Ciappo, like all the similar exhibits, difficulties are even greater, due to the fact that, as other sites in the area of the Finale, is an "open", easily editable by external agents: atmospheric, and above all human. It is a known fact that this complex has been and is, as yet, explored (as shown by the names given in this report), although less frequently, given the lush vegetation that invades it.

Conclusions

It would be desirable to encourage further study of this and other complexes, not least from the standpoint of archaeoastronomy, this, at present seems the most promising and challenging.

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Photo 1: Steps on the Rock

Photo 2: Petroglyphs

Photo 3: Petroglyphs

Photo 4: Petroglyphs

Photo 5: Petroglyphs

Photo 6: Perennial Water Well

Photo 7: The Pool

Photo 8: The Pool

Photo 9: The Cheeses

Photo 10: The Cheeses